

**FRACTURE TOUGHNESS IN MODE I : A COMPARISON EXERCISE OF
VARIOUS TEST METHODS**

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ABSTRACT

Measurement of strain energy release rate in Mode I is now extensively developed in industrial and research laboratories as it represents a good assessment of composites behaviour relatively to delamination. Results obtained by four French laboratories -for T300/5208 carbon fibre-epoxy composites- have been compared and systematic influence of some data reduction schemes are put forward. It is also emphasized that the choice of specimen geometry -mainly thickness- and the condition of measurement -during crack propagation or at crack arrest- strongly influence G_{IC} values and must be carefully precised for any valuable comparison between results originated from different sources.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is now well recognized that delamination -concurrently with cracking of transverse plies- is a major mode of ruine for laminated carbon fiber-epoxy composite materials.

Delaminations may be classified into two categories :

- delaminations resulting from fabrication defects
- delaminations due to the laminate nature of composite materials (free edge effects along the sides or around the attachment holes of the structure, impact damage).

However, in both cases fracture criteria based upon estimation of ply by ply fracture (ex. TSAI, HILL etc) are no more of great use.

A more phenomenological approach based upon analytical methods requires a complete knowledge of material behaviour in terms of fracture mechanics.

In this respect experiments for assessment of fracture toughness are now systematically introduced into programs of characterization of composite materials.

As G_{IC} values are lower than G_{IIC} or G_{IIIC} [1, 2], delamination is mainly caused by the Mode I component of stresses.

Measurement of G_{IC} is therefore mostly chosen for toughness assessment. Results generated in four French laboratories are presented hereafter. Two of them are laboratories of aerospace industry (Avion Marcel Dassault-Bréguet Aviation and Aérospatiale Central Laboratory) and the two others belong to governmental establishments (Centre d'Etudes Aéronautiques de Toulouse and Office National d'Etudes et de Recherches Aérospatiales). These four laboratories will be subsequently referred as AMD-BA, AS, CEAT and ONERA respectively.

Even if the research programs were not formally connected, a detailed examination of the results achieved in the four laboratories shows that the various extensions from a common framework can lead to a survey of technics for G_{IC} measurements -with comparison of corresponding results- and of the influences of some experimental factors not to be neglected.

2. TEST METHODS

Each laboratory used the so-called "double-cantilever beam" specimen. These specimens -except AMD-BA specimens- are parallel sided coupons of unidirectional composites with a teflon film separator inserted in the midplane a crack starter. Aluminium tabs are bonded to the specimens for attachment to the tensile machine (fig. 1).

As crack propagation must be initiated from a "natural crack", this condition may be fulfilled by two ways :

- hand-made precracking (for instance by forcing a razor blade)
- precracking by a first tension solicitation.

The test itself consists in loading the specimen up to crack propagation. During the propagation changes of load, displacement and crack length are simultaneously monitored. The load is sometimes intermittently returned to zero when measurement of compliance is needed for data reduction (fig. 2).

Analysing one step of this process some noteworthy points can be observed (fig. 3) :

- I initiation of propagation (beginning of non-linearity also detected by acoustic emission)

- M maximum load
- C current point during crack propagation
- S stopping of the displacement of the tensile machine
- A crack-arrest after a period of stabilization SA.

Fig. 1. Test specimen geometry.

Fig. 2. Typical load-deflection curve.

Fig. 3. Typical loading and unloading cycle.

This description corresponds to the more complete cycle which can be carried out. It can be thoroughly followed (CEAT) or simplified :

- displacement can be returned to zero immediately after stopping the tensile machine (AMD-BA, WILKINS [3])
- displacement can be stopped at the maximum load (ONERA)
- displacement can be continued up to the final fracture of the specimen.

In most cases however the loading process is not precised in the literature even though measured values of G_{IC} may be a function of measurement point.

3. DATA REDUCTION SCHEMES

Data reduction schemes are all based on the definition of the "critical strain energy release rate" G_{IC} .

$$G_{IC} = - \frac{dW}{dS} \quad (1)$$

which corresponds to the total energy change dW (internal and external) related to the creation of a new surface dS .

Through the assumption of linear elastic response of the material (1) results in the IRWIN strain energy release rate relationship :

$$G_{IC} = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (2)$$

where a and b are geometrical dimensions defined fig. 1 and P and C stand respectively for the critical load at crack extension and the compliance, $C = \frac{\delta}{P}$, of the specimen.

Data reduction schemes can be classified into three main ranges. From the lot of methods described in the literature the most representation ones are hereunder reported.

Methods based upon application of beam theory

1) Direct application

$$C = \frac{2a^3}{3EI} \quad (3)$$

where E stands for the Young's modulus and I for the moment of inertia of one beam. Introducing (3) into (2)

$$G_{IC} = \frac{P^2 a^2}{EIb} \quad (4)$$

2) Direct application of beam theory with correction for shear strain [4] :

$$C = \frac{2a^3}{3EI} + \frac{3a}{2Gb^2h} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{and } G_{IC} = \frac{P^2 a^2}{EIb} + \frac{3P^2}{2Gb^2h} \quad (6)$$

3) Application of beam theory (same as 1) with direct assessment of the Young's modulus [5]

$$\text{from (3) } C = \frac{\delta}{P} = \frac{2a^3}{3EI}$$

$$\text{or } E = \frac{2a^3 P}{3\delta I} \quad (7)$$

where δ is the deflection of the specimen.

Reintroducing (7) into (4)

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3P\delta}{2ab} \quad (8)$$

4) Ashizawa's method [6]

Observing that apparent flexure modulus E is a function of crack length, Ashizawa introduces in the expression of $\frac{dC}{da}$ the derivative E' of E with respect to a

$$\frac{dC}{da} = \frac{2a^3}{Eb^3} \left[1 - \frac{aE'}{3E} \right] \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Setting } E = E_0 \left[1 - \frac{a_0}{a} \right]$$

where E_0 and a_0 are constants evaluated by experimental fitting :

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{P\delta}{ba} \left[\frac{3a - 4a_0}{3(a - a_0)} \right] \quad (10)$$

Methods based upon polynomial fitting of experimentally measured compliance

From a series of loading and unloading during crack propagation, C is

set into the form of a third degree polynomial :

$$C = A a^3 + B a^2 + D a + E$$

where coefficients A, B, D, E are calculated through the best fit of experimental curves.

The polynomial can be

- 5) complete
- 6) with only coefficient A [3] (reference to method nr. 1)
- 7) with only coefficients A, D, E (reference to method nr. 2)
- 8) Berry's method [7]

Using an empirical generalization of relation (3) (or of method nr. 6), Berry assumes :

$$C = R a^n \quad (11)$$

where R and n are constant experimentally determined from the relationship

$$\log\left(\frac{P}{\delta}\right) = -\log R - n \log a \quad (12)$$

and a least square fitting to eq. (12) from a series of loading and unloading curves.

Methods based upon energy area integration [5]

Two ways can be followed for application of these methods.

- 9) direct measurement on the diagram of the area between loading and unloading curves after a finite propagation (fig. 3)

$$G_{IC} = \frac{\Delta S}{\Delta A} = \frac{1}{b} \frac{\Delta S}{\Delta a} \quad (13)$$

- 10) assuming that curves (P, δ) during loading, crack propagation and unloading can be approximated by straight lines :

$$G_{IC} = \frac{1}{2b\Delta a} (P_1 \delta_2 - P_2 \delta_1) \quad (14)$$

11) Case of width tapered double cantilever beam specimen

The specimen is designed in such a way that :

$$\frac{b}{a} = 2 \operatorname{tg} \alpha \quad (15)$$

Each of the previous methods can be applied, for instance rewriting (3) :

$$C = \frac{8a^3}{Ebh^3} = \frac{4a^2}{Eh^3 \operatorname{tg} \alpha} \quad (16)$$

$$G_{IC} = \frac{2P^2}{Eh^3 \operatorname{tg}^2 \alpha}$$

The crack length no longer appears and as long as G_{IC} is constant during crack propagation, the load P remains constant as well.

E can be estimated from one or several loading curves and method 11) is then equivalent to method 3).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results obtained by the 4 laboratories are summarized table 1 where some experimental features are also precised.

TABLE 1
T300/5208 values from the 4 laboratories

Estab- lissements	Data re- duction methods	Results $G_{IC}(J/m^2)$	Nbr. of spe- cimens Standard deviation	Specimen geometry Fibre content	Tension rate	Points of measurement (see fig. 3)
CEAT	3) Whitney	102.2	n=10* SD=6.5%	b=20mm	1 mm/mn	maximum load (point M)
	6) C=Aa ³	101.8	SD=6.4%	2h=4 mm		
	7) C=Aa ³ +Da+E	91.8	SD=6.0%	(32 plies)		
	8) Berry	91	SD=4.9%	Vf=64%		
	10) Approxi- mate area int. method	88.6	SD=3.9%			
	Mean value	95.2	SD=5.9% *5 measure- ments by specimen			
AS	1) Beam theory	84.5	n=15** SD=7.3%	b=20mm	2 mm/mn	Initiation of propagation (point I) not very dif- ferent from point M
	3) Whitney	94.5	SD=7.6%	2h=4 mm		
	4) Ashizawa	89.6	SD=7.1%	(32 plies)		
	5) C=Aa ³ +Ba ² +Da+E	92.4	SD=9.2%	Vf=63%		
	6) C=Aa ³	89.8	SD=7.8%			
	8) Berry	89.7	SD=7.0%			
	9) area int. method	86.0	SD=8.3%			
	Mean value	89.5	SD=3.6% **5 to 8 measure- ments by specimen			
	AMD-BA	11) with ta- pered DCB (method identical to 3)	100 to 150 for crack propagation of 30 mm	n=3		
ONERA	7) C=Aa ³ +Da+E	85	n=3*** SD=5.2%	b=12.5 mm 2h=1.65 mm (14 plies)	0.1 mm/mn	Crack arrest (point A)
			n=7*** SD=7%	b=12.5 mm 2h=1.65 mm (14 plies) +A1 support beams (2x12.5 mm)		
			54 to 88 for crack propagation of 50 mm	***10 measure- ments by spe- cimen Vf=65 mm		

Concerning data reduction schemes, CEAT and AS results represent an extensive comparison between much various methods. Keeping in mind that both laboratories make use the same type of specimen it can be pointed out

that :

- method nr. 1 takes into account the Young's modulus as measured for instance from tension tests. However, for composite materials, the extensional modulus which is introduced into (3) is greater than the flexure modulus which should rather be used [6]. Derived values of G_{IC} are therefore too low,
- conversely method nr. 3 provides the highest values of G_{IC} . The flexure modulus is actually derived through the entire loading curve which commonly display some non-linearity. Measurement of δ integrates such phenomena as plasticity, micro-damage at crack tip etc... and as value of E is consequently lower than a purely elastic one, values of G_{IC} derived from (8) are higher than other ones,
- other methods do not display systematic tendencies (when CEAT and AS results are considered as a whole) with the exception of energy-area integration methods 9) and 10) whose low values will be considered in section 4.

In any case, the scattering between results reduced from one of the various method is greater than the scattering between mean values issued from these methods.

With the exception of afore-mentioned ones : 1), 3), 9) and 10) all the methods can be considered as equivalent.

Results from AMD-BA and ONERA, originated from different experimental conditions will be considered in section 4.

4. EXPERIMENTAL PARAMETERS INFLUENCING G_{IC} MEASUREMENTS

4.1. R curve phenomenon

In table I, two results are noteworthy (AMD-BA and ONERA second result) as values of G_{IC} are not constant but increase with the length of crack propagation. As can be observed these results correspond to the thickest tested specimens (8.5 mm for AMD-BA and 1.65 mm of composite + 25 mm for aluminium supports, equivalent to a 22.8 mm composite specimen for ONERA).

To assess the influence of specimen thickness upon G_{IC} values 3 types of specimens have been tested at ONERA :

- unstiffened specimens $[0]_{14}$,
- specimens stiffened by aluminium beams : $[0]_{14}$ + aluminium,
- specimens stiffened by steel beams : $[0]_{14}$ + steel.

Mean results reduced through method nr. 7 are reported fig. 4. For

comparison, G_{IC} of neat 5208 resin, measured as for composites, is also reported.

Fig. 4. G_{IC} Versus Crack Length.

It can be noticed that G_{IC} increases at the beginning of crack growth before stabilizing (except for steel supported specimens for which measurement of G_{IC} is only possible for long cracks -and low loads- owing to the too weak adhesion between steel and composite).

For slender (or flexible) specimens G_{IC} increase only over a short length before stabilization. As precracking is often realized through a first crack propagation under tension whose result is not taken into account (see section 2), R curve phenomenon is then concealed and published results are often in fact "stabilized" values of G_{IC} .

R curve phenomenon has often been ascribed to the formation of fibre bridges connecting fracture surfaces [8] (G_{IC} values for neat resin are therefore constant during the whole crack growth). Slender specimens are more flexible than thick ones and the greater opening of the crack leads to an early fracture of the first created bridges, G_{IC} then stabilizes after a short crack growth [9]. For observation of R curve of these specimens, a very careful short precracking is demanded.

Stabilized values of G_{IC} depend themselves on the stiffness of the specimens and cannot therefore be considered as intrinsic values of the material. They are only valuable relatively with each other provided that specimens thicknesses are themselves comparable.

4.2. Dynamic effects

In section 2 and fig. 3, 5 different points have been precised for which G_{IC} can be calculated. From a loading cycle where tensile machine stroke is stopped at maximum load (points M and S identical), G_{IC} have been measured at ONERA during crack growth from an aluminium supported $[0]_{14}$ composite specimen. Results are reported fig. 5 and some characteristic features can be pointed out :

G_{IC} values display a double evolution during crack growth :

- the first one during a loading cycle is clearly connected to a dynamic effect. G_{IC} values corresponding to initiation, maximum load and crack arrest are different and $G_{IC_A} < G_{IC_I} < G_{IC_M}$.

T300/5208 $[0]_{14}$ + aluminium beams 0 % H.R.

Fig. 5. G_{IC} values for 6 loading and unloading cycles.

- G_{IC_I} , G_{IC_M} and G_{IC_A} can be fitted by 3 curves : R_I , R_M , R_A .

Experiments varying loading rate [9] clearly show that whereas the R curve corresponding to points A is obviously independent of the displacement rate, R_I and R_M are not. As a matter of fact as crack-growth in DCB specimens should be stable for displacement controlled tests, any point above the R_A curve is out of equilibrium and a part of mechanical work is consummated by kinetics energy.

The gap between R_A , R_I and R_M curves depends upon the equilibrium lag which itself depends upon the loading rate of the specimen $\frac{dG}{dt}$. $\frac{dG}{dt}$ is a function of both displacement rate and stiffness of the specimen.

For stiff specimens and/or high tensile rate R_I , R_M and R_A curves are very different and high values of G_{IC} are then obtained. As dynamic effects are cumulative with R curve effects, G_{IC} values are then very high and dependent upon crack length (AMD-BA and [10]).

Conversely, for low speed and/or flexible specimens, R_I and R_M curves are not significantly different from R_A curve and corresponding G_{IC} can be classed as static measurements.

Differences between G_{IC_I} , G_{IC_M} and G_{IC_A} can also be assessed in evaluating G_{IC} through energy area integration methods 9) or 10). G_{IC} values then integrate variations during the whole loading cycle and are lower than G_{IC} calculated from other methods taking into consideration either points I or M (see section 3 and table 1).

5. CONCLUSIONS

G_{IC} of unidirectional composite materials have been measured in 4 French laboratories with double cantilever beam specimens.

From the comparison between the results derived from various data reduction schemes, it has been established that some of them can lead to systematic variations when the others can be considered as equivalent.

Assessment of experimental parameters like specimen thickness, loading rate and measurement points clearly show that a great care is needed for comparison between results derived from different sources.

Effects of materials parameters themselves :

- comparison between various materials (or batches), influence of type of resin, fibre or interface, influence of fibre volume fraction, etc...
- effect of temperature, moisture,

can therefore only be properly assessed if afore-mentioned conditions are fulfilled.

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